

Adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Library Services for National Development: A Review of Literature

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Abstract

One of the most significant contemporary technologies that have developed recently is the adoption of artificial intelligence, which has played a significant role in the advancement of institutions, particularly the scope of libraries. The purpose of this study was to describe the role of artificial intelligence adoption in library services for national development, as well as to identify the reality of using AI applications in libraries to enhance knowledge management, expose the link between AI applications and their capacity to develop technical and administrative processes in libraries of knowledge management and understand the difficulties and advantages facing the field. The study's descriptive methodology, which focuses on adopting artificial intelligence in library services, was used to analyse the content of numerous literature reviews. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in library services, problems, and advantages are the main topics of this study; it also focuses on the idea of library services for national development, applications of artificial intelligence in library services, such as the use of expert systems in acquisition, cataloguing, classification, and reference services, as well as the use of robotics in library operations. The study concluded that there was a strong case for libraries to realign themselves to benefit somewhat from artificial intelligence. The study recommended increasing field studies to investigate the requirements of artificial intelligence technologies, diversity in the services provided by artificial intelligence in the library, and effective activation of those services for libraries and information centres to keep up with the changes in artificial intelligence and make the right investments for knowledge management.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), Library services, knowledge management, national development

Introduction

There is no doubt that artificial intelligence (AI) has been transforming our lives, workplaces, and homes in recent times. According to Nwakunor (2021), AI consists of robots that are directed by computers and have human-like intelligence. Nowadays, AI gadgets may be found in our homes in the shape of robot vacuum cleaners, gadgets that keep an eye on the moisture content of the garden, or gadgets that automatically order more laundry detergent. Similarly, robots work alongside people on the production floor, distribute components, or carry out laborious or even hazardous duties. AI is now widely acknowledged as a tool that is essential for increasing productivity and corporate effectiveness (Sukumar, 2024). It is utilized in various fields, including libraries, business, medical, and the military. A computer system capable of voice recognition, decision-making, and language comprehension ordinarily needs human intellect. Information specialists can leverage these innovative new technologies to improve their services and assist consumers in finding and accessing specific information more quickly and conveniently. AI is changing how information is handled and looked for. Although there have been concerns from some quarters that AI lacks the "human touch," can replace human jobs, can malfunction and act contrary to what is programmed in them, and can be misused, leading to mass-scale destruction, among other things, its advantages have far outweighed the perceived challenges, as noted by Mogali (2015).

Modern libraries increasingly serve as digital service providers rather than just repositories for printed materials (Tella, 2020). The extensive use of computer systems, ongoing reliance on computer networks, the rapid development of the web and Internet, and increased quantity and quality of information may all contribute to this trend. Several libraries have adopted revolutionary information storage, retrieval, and dissemination systems. A library network has been established due to the analogue to digital conversion of information hubs and libraries. This technique aids multiple layers of resource generation, sharing, and utilisation. ICTs are being utilised to both create and access electronic sources, including electronic journals, online and CD-ROM databases, web-based information resources, and a wide variety of other kinds of electronic information resources (Owolabi et al., 2022).

The University of Lagos became the first organisation in Nigeria to use artificial intelligence thanks to Platform Capital's investment in June 2020 (Ogunleye, 2021). According to information provided by Roboscholar, the robots are "cloud-based intelligent humanoid robots," and they have the following features: face recognition, surveillance technology, Open API, data management, advertisement and promotion, bookshelf management, research, customizable, and entry validation (University of Lagos, 2020). In today's wireless and

connected environment, integrating cutting-edge innovative technology into normal library operations is the most practical way to achieve new goals and objectives. Libraries and librarians are making efforts to keep up with the times in the digital era.

Notably, most AI capabilities, including auto-suggest, relevance rating, auto-recommendation, bookmarking, and voice recognition, are already widely used in word processing and search functions in online and mobile applications (Adejo, & Misau, 2021). Several features may be incorporated to make library services more interactive and user-friendly. Information is available fast and in novel ways thanks to the use of AI in libraries. One example of this is using voice commands to do informative searches. ICT is the main force behind the current information environment. In order to deliver innovative information services that meet consumers' changing requirements, there is a strong dependence on new technological breakthroughs. To efficiently deliver information services that satisfy the expectations of the modern world, libraries must adapt and incorporate cutting-edge technology, such as artificial intelligence. However, the worrying fact that many libraries in Nigeria do not fully use the benefits of AI for efficient service delivery to local and remote customers is concerning. In order to assist in the delivery of good and efficient services to students, researchers, and staff, this study examines the potential uses of AI in libraries.

The modern information environment is heavily reliant on ICT. In order to provide dynamic and cutting-edge information services that match the shifting demands of the customers, there is a high level of dependency on new technical advancements. Adoption and integration of cutting-edge technology like artificial intelligence are required for libraries to deliver excellent information services that address the present concerns. However, the fact that many libraries in Nigeria are not completely using the benefits of AI for efficient service delivery to both local and remote customers is concerning. The study's objectives were to determine the reality of using AI applications in libraries and the connection between AI applications' capacity to create technical and administrative procedures in libraries. In order to explore potential areas where libraries could implement AI to promote quality and effective service delivery to students, researchers, and faculty, the study applied the Descriptive method by content analysis of the literature review with the most significant and related published literature.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate how libraries could best utilise cutting-edge technology like AI and robotics to support high-quality and user-friendly services in the digital era. It aims to

reawaken the responsibilities of libraries in satisfying consumers' evolving demands and expectations through AI. More precisely, this investigation aims to:

1. Learn how cutting-edge technologies can help libraries offer better services.
2. Be aware of the potential applications of AI in providing library services.
3. Awareness of libraries' difficulties while implementing artificial intelligence applications.

Literature Review

The Concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

According to Irizarry-Nones, Palepu, and Wallace (2017), artificial intelligence is the programming and development of computers to carry out tasks requiring human intellect, such as speech recognition, decision-making, visual perception, language translation, conversing, and emotional emotions. The technology that gives robots the ability to plan, learn, reason, solve problems, move, and, to some extent, be creative is known as artificial intelligence, according to Heath (2018). Liu (2016) described AI as intelligent devices or systems that mimic human intelligence functions. According to Oname and Alex-Nmecha (2020), artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science that focuses on how computers learn (Machine Learning), interpret information, and perceive the world via their eyes, including character recognition, image analysis, 3D perception, and eye function modelling. It also covers voice recognition, speech creation, the comprehension and use of natural language (also known as NLP), and expert systems, which are receiving increasing attention. Artificial intelligence emphasizes non-algorithmic approaches to problem resolution and symbol interpretation. AI relies on the ability to map symbols. Informational researchers have many fantastic prospects thanks to new applications, including multimedia systems, digital libraries, GISs, and e-commerce.

On the other hand, artificial intelligence is developed or generated by humans instead of occurring naturally, especially as a duplicate of anything natural (Vijayakumar & Sheshadri, 2019). Intelligence is the capacity to reason, absorb knowledge and skills, and use them when appropriate. Thus, developing computers or other devices that observe, learn, reason, and behave like humans might be classified as artificial intelligence. Robot vacuums that can scan a room's size, recognise barriers like furniture, and then recall the most effective path to clean successfully are examples of artificial intelligence (AI). Other examples include Google Maps, which may provide route directions, an estimated travel time, and time updates; virtual assistants like Siri or Alexa; smart thermostats; face recognition; and so on. Given the

preceding, Liu (2011) essentially categorised artificial intelligence (AI) systems from two distinct approaches, as shown below:

1. Their level of intellect. According to this viewpoint, artificial intelligence systems are divided into four categories: utility-based systems, goal-oriented systems, learning systems, and systems that can teach computer programming. Reflex agents can react to stimuli from heat sensors, light sensors, and motion detectors.
2. How they work. According to this perspective, artificial intelligence systems may be divided into four types: mobile systems that can move independently from one location to another for a job, reactive systems, Internet-based systems, and collaborative systems.

The majority of the computers and mobile phones being created today include artificial intelligence elements, and we have undoubtedly used them without realising they are intelligent devices. They now affect many of our regular computing tasks.

Libraries and National Development

Few libraries, according to Ogbonnaya (2020), exist in a vacuum and are entirely responsible for themselves. Thus, there is always a bigger context for evaluating the quality of libraries, namely, what and how effectively does the library contribute to attaining the overarching goals of the parent constituencies? The main goal of libraries in the twenty-first century must be to connect themselves with the frameworks of higher education and the standards by which such organizations are evaluated, especially in a climate of growing economic pressure, structural change, and technological innovation. Bokoh, Ajiboye, and Bello (2023) said the micro evaluation of libraries has provided numerous opportunities for in-depth research. However, there are still no agreed-upon, impartial methods for calculating the value of libraries and incorporating them into procedures like educational evaluation and graduate programme rankings.

According to Olubiyo, (2022), libraries give individuals information, knowledge, skill, and technique so they may comprehend their obligations to their families, communities, and nation. Libraries have significantly improved the quality of life in any civilization. Ofodu and Okwoli (2023) assert that a library is an essential tool that may be utilised to unlock many of a country's shut doors. A nation experiences meteoric socioeconomic growth as soon as it acknowledges the role of libraries as development catalysts. However, it's critical to comprehend how libraries could strengthen the economy for a developing country like Nigeria. When there is no

illiteracy, people become more informed and behave as respectable citizens should. It is important to note that the country will be in better shape if people live responsibly.

Application of Artificial Intelligence in Library Services

According to the Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (CILIP, 2021), new technologies are changing not only people's everyday lives but also worldwide trends and many other facets of society. Traditional jobs requiring significant change require new skills, opportunities, and challenges. Librarians and their responsibilities in the contemporary library environment are all impacted by this new revolution.

Incorporating cutting-edge technology like artificial intelligence into their core services was difficult for many university libraries in Nigeria (Akinola, 2023). After a global pandemic broke out in 2020, there has been an increased requirement for deploying cutting-edge technology to support library service operations (Owolabi et al., 2022). Libraries in Nigeria should implement AI for several reasons, including changing user behaviour, improving the information environment, and more. Using intelligent Internet-connected gadgets, employing digital high-tech products in homes, and incorporating AI helpers into daily activities are additional advancements in the technological era (Poole, 2020).

Libraries may maintain their relevance in the future, accept additional duties and services, and avoid becoming out of the current by utilising machine learning for library applications. However, in the library's journey, overcoming the obstacles to AI adoption is crucial (Oniovoghai, Idiodi, & Urhiewhu, 2023). The concept of artificial intelligence is broad and may be used to all facets of libraries to make them more intelligent. The introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) into institutions for the delivery of services has reportedly opened doors for major issues impacting traditional library routine services to be promptly handled, according to Oniovoghai, Idiodi & Urhiewhu (2023).

The quality of library services in the information age must be improved, according to Tella (2020), if libraries are to orient themselves to make use of the potential of artificial intelligence. Due to the quicker access to information, this application in libraries will help give better search and information services, exciting both library personnel and users. Akinyemi (2023) said enhancement of many librarians' job duties, including cataloguing, indexing, information retrieval, reference, and other jobs, has been made possible by using artificial intelligence (AI) in library services delivery. Speech recognition, machine translation, and library robots are just a few of its uses. The University of Lagos is currently the only institution in Nigeria to have

implemented the use of artificial intelligence in some library services and operations, and the use of artificial intelligence in library services and operations is still not widely known among library professionals, according to Tunde et al. (2022).

Libraries are putting themselves in a position to benefit from cognitive computing applications in general and artificial intelligence applications in particular, which are of potential value as a tool for improving the quality of library services. Furthermore, Kristin (2016) clarifies that libraries might alter concentration and attention through AI applications. AI provides a helpful shortcut for using this information and achieving better results. The methods for implementing artificial intelligence in library services in Nigeria are listed.

Application of Expert System in Library Acquisition

Artificial intelligence (AI) has given rise to the notion of an expert system, which necessitates a break from traditional programming methods. According to Mogali (2015), the most often used artificial intelligence programs are expert systems, which are computer programmes that represent human mentions of artificial intelligence developed with the intention of electro-mechanical devices taking the place of humans. McCarthy (2016) adds that an expert system is a type of computer program for issue solving that performs well in a particular problem domain that is seen to be challenging and calls for certain knowledge and abilities. According to Giarratano and Riley (2014), expert systems are a subset of artificial intelligence that heavily relies on specialised knowledge to handle issues at the level of human experts. An expert system is a computer program that simulates a human expert's decision-making process. It solves issues that require human competence by applying knowledge and reasoning skills. According to Abram (2018), an expert system uses a body of knowledge to reason its way through challenging challenges. It is mainly expressed as rules rather than using a traditional procedural code. Expert and non-expert knowledge and information from manuals, databases, journals, and textbooks are coded and added to the system. The system's inference and reasoning processes employ this coded knowledge to provide advice as needed. Expert systems aim to emulate human specialists through their capacity to provide guidance, instruct, and carry out intelligent activities. This system makes it possible to apply and benefit from the notion of a true expert system to solve problems that arise in everyday life, particularly in libraries.

Application of Expert System in Cataloguing and Classification

One of the oldest library crafts is cataloguing. Recent efforts to automate cataloguing using expert systems have focused on descriptive cataloguing since it is thought to be rule-based (Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules-2). Expert systems have been developed to create Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC) records and to apply some of the rules in Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules-2 for cataloguing (AACR-2). Roy Chang developed a cataloguing expert system based on the rules in AACR-2. He determined that its usefulness was limited because the system could not interpret the rules. In this opinion, cataloguing problems today are too widespread to employ an expert system (Chang, 1990). Artificial intelligence techniques can be applied in one of two ways to cataloguing:

- a. A human-machine interaction where the support system and intermediary share intellectual work;
- b. A text created online may be transferred through knowledge-based systems, and the cataloguing process can be completed without the need for an intermediary's intellectual input by using b. An Expert System with total cataloguing capacity connected to an electronic publishing system.

The essential process in the organisation of knowledge is classification. Because of this, it is significant in all knowledge organisation systems in libraries and information centres. The following are some examples of expert system applications in the domain of library classifications:

- a. Coal SORT is a hypothetical browser that may be used as a search or indexing tool. Its main components are a frame-based semantic network and the software required to enable users to navigate the conceptual structure and see specific areas of the network. The semantic network contains practically all of the expert knowledge present in the system.
- b. EP-X: The Environmental Pollution Expert (EP-X) and coal SORT both focus on upgrading interfaces using a knowledge-based approach, which gives them some similarities. EP-X's knowledge base consists of a set of templates that represent patterns known as the pragmatic connection among ideas and a hierarchical frame-based semantic network of concepts. Conceptual information is the term used to describe these patterns.
- c. BIOSIS: Using procedural knowledge and knowledge-based devices, BIOSIS automatically allocates documents to different categories. It is made to help indexers.

To assign as many categories as feasible of those that would be allocated by human indexers, BIOSIS leverages the information in the titles of biological materials. The organized and useful information representation provided by the indexing languages is extremely advantageous for applications using artificial intelligence.

Applications of Expert Systems in Reference Services

Saving library users' time and delivering targeted information as soon as possible are two of any library's main goals. Thus, the term "Reference Service" refers to giving readers personal attention to satisfy their unique demands (Chandwani, 2010). Dr. S. R. Ranganathan asserts that reference services are now available to distant users and library patrons in the current technological and communication environment. The primary goal of the e-reference service, digital reference service, virtual reference service, or pin-pointed reference service is to promptly and thoroughly assist information searchers with any questions they may have. Locating resources and information would be made easier for users by using expert systems. According to Kemp (1988), expert systems have the ability to ask users what kind of knowledge they want and then present them with resources that could have it.

An expert system called Reference Advisory Systems (RAS) was created at San Diego State University to help with reference services. Using a natural language interface, the RAS system offers reference services in computer science, materials science, and public health nursing. A reference advisory system (RAS) is an expert system available to the public that suggests references depending on users' information needs. It is intended to function even without the "expert." The RAS's key mark is its simplicity of updating and building. Carande (1989).

The expert system must be utilized in the following ways to enhance the Reference Librarian:

- a. **Research:** This system was created to provide users with suggested sites to check up on certain questions. It also instructs reference techniques or provides computerized assistance for working information professionals and librarians.
- b. **Pointer:** Although it is a computer-assisted reference programme, it is also known as a knowledge-based system. It leads customers towards citation sources.
- c. **Online Reference Assistance (ORA):** This method aims to encourage the assistance of a reference librarian for inquiries of low and medium level by utilizing a variety of technologies. Examples include databases that seem like videotext, computer-assisted

learning modules, and knowledge-based systems. ORA consists of directional transactions, such as library locations, services, and regulations.

- d. **Answer-man:** A knowledge-based system assists users with ag-related reference inquiries. It contains several choices that let you choose the right tool and inquiry topic. It can serve as a front-end to external databases and CD-ROM reference resources or as a system for consultation.
- e. **PLEXUS:** This is primarily a referral resource for public libraries. It offers advice on utilising references, finding specific subject-specific material, where to find references, and how to use libraries. The systems mentioned above are advisories for finding factual information and reference materials.

Applications of Robotics in Library Activities

Adejo and Misau (2021) define a robot as an autonomously controlled, reprogrammable, multi-purpose manipulator that can be programmed in three or more axes and used in automation applications. Robots can be stationary or mobile. Fernandez (2016) looks at the potential effects of robots on libraries. Nancy (2016) addresses the differences between artificial intelligence and intelligent agents and their possible future applications. The study looks at their advantages, disadvantages, and challenges specific to libraries and provides examples of how librarians might utilise them. With so many AI applications, librarians will have the opportunity to shift focus and attention, according to Finley (2019), who commented on the significance of robots in library operations. This is because libraries and librarians need to adapt to the new information environment of the twenty-first century, which has changed how information is accessed and disseminated. According to Arlitsch and Newell (2017), machine learning techniques, massive data availability, and faster networks have all contributed to the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), which has the potential to transform a wide range of businesses, including libraries, drastically. They also look at the implications of automation for politics and society, the dangers and possibilities facing libraries, and its impact on employment. Garcia-Febo (2019) addresses the use of AI networks in libraries and offers insights into the difficulties posed by technological advancements like AI and machine learning, including issues with access to information, privacy, and intellectual freedom.

Issues with Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Libraries Services Delivery

For AI to be used effectively in libraries, several challenges come with its acceptance, just as with other technologies. According to Robinson (2018) and Yusuf, Adebayo, Bello, and Kayode (2022), these problems include the following:

Lack of Finance: Cultural institutions are frequently the first to experience budget cuts when government funding declines and political or economic developments are underway. Financial instability is becoming a major worry for libraries. The battle for institutional or governmental financing resembles the chicken-and-egg dilemma in many respects. Libraries must integrate new technology to enhance the user experience for today's patrons - all of which demand more cash - to meet expectations for value for money and cost-effective practices. Today's libraries frequently find themselves in a financial bind because they cannot demonstrate their worth without extra money.

Reluctance to accept new technology and adjust workflow procedures: Budget constraints are one barrier preventing libraries from using AI and other technologies. SCOUNL (2017) claims that library personnel frequently exhibit reluctance to change and even a protective attitude toward technological transformation.

Developing skills gaps: The digitization of information has influenced both library operations and systems. Since the digital world is now just as significant as the physical one, if not more so, libraries must learn new skills to remain competent and provide better services to users in the digital era. For these services to be effective, new competencies are needed, such as increased digital fluency, the capacity to deliver the most pertinent materials quickly, and the ability to enable hands-on, creative activities.

Fear of potential dangers from AI: In addition to everything previously said, libraries appear to resist internal adoption of technology, particularly AI technology, due to several serious worries about the possible negative consequences of this disruptive technology on libraries. Lauren (2022) lists some of the main challenges librarians mentioned: Librarians will be replaced by AI (or robots). The concern of librarians losing their jobs to AI robots is understandable given the disturbing statistic that 38% of jobs are in great danger of being replaced by AI in the years to come; AI's effectiveness will make human creativity and empathy unnecessary, leading to a future where the library's relationship with its community and vital human traits are rare and devalued; AI would amplify injustices including inequality, bigotry, and discrimination as well as contribute to the spread of false information. Search engine algorithms already lack some fundamental neutrality, and other instances demonstrate how

readily AI might be used as a discriminatory instrument. It may also be exploited to spread misinformation and bias or be utilized politically. In the current digital era, data privacy is even more crucial to libraries and might be jeopardized by AI.

Benefits of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Library Activities

Robinson (2018) presented a few ways that AI applications might add immediate, quantifiable value to libraries despite some of the difficulties encountered with the implementation of AI in libraries:

Boost operational effectiveness: By enhancing service performance and lowering operating costs through process automation, improved research data management, and Digital Asset Management (DAM), libraries may recognize and amplify operational efficiencies. In support of this, Divayana et al. (2015) cited a few benefits of AI for library operations, including but not limited to its capacity for speedy completion of tasks. Machine learning may improve collection analysis, visualization, and preservation and lower service delivery costs using the library's workflows and digital resources. Adopting cutting-edge Library Services Platforms (LSP) can assist in creating initiatives that boost operational effectiveness even further.

Improve user experience and introduce new services to attract greater audiences: Machine learning algorithms can immediately tailor information from thousands of resources by optimising search engine results using Chatbots and location-based services, replacing the manual sorting of only a portion of that data. To discover requirements and provide excellent, engaging customer experiences, AI systems may also collect data on user touch points, previous interactions, and behaviour. More effective learning involves creating individualized, accurate research recommendations and matching search results with the particular student's level of expertise.

Reduce the amount of manual daily regular search and reference activities to help librarians reach their new objectives: Implementing AI can lessen human inefficiencies and mistakes. Additionally, this automation frees library employees to concentrate on more challenging and high-value jobs like helping lecturers create reading lists, guiding students in improving their research, creating library collections, and similar activities.

Create a solid foundation for libraries in the new intellectual information environment: By assisting in the discovery of linkages to massive data sets that might otherwise go unnoticed, AI technology can facilitate disciplinary alignment throughout academic study. Additionally,

libraries may contribute to the seamless flow of data and research across industries and disciplines by collaborating with open publication organisations and using research methods that work with other institutions. Their collections become easier to find, search for, and analyse, ultimately fostering the development of a robust, top-notch worldwide network of resources. The IFLA Statement (2020) recommends effective AI deployment to capitalise on the technology and reap its many benefits. They provide the following advice for libraries: "Libraries may educate users about AI and support their success in a society that employs AI more extensively. Integrate artificial intelligence and machine learning into daily tasks: Libraries may fund superior, moral AI research. Additionally, correct policies must be developed and implemented before, during, and after the deployment of AI in African university libraries.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Nigerian libraries using artificial intelligence have been viewed as a fresh source of inspiration for the growth of intelligent libraries. To keep up with current worldwide trends, librarians have started implementing artificial technology in some specialised sections of their libraries. Some cutting-edge applications of artificial intelligence to library operations include Robotics and expert systems in library activities such as acquisition, cataloguing, classification, and reference services. Therefore, applying AI to library services removes difficult and demanding tasks from which people may experience fewer mistakes and defects, facilitates access to research materials, and mitigates the absence of human engagement and touch.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, it is advised that all libraries across the nation focus on using or adopting artificial intelligence in their library operating systems.

- i. In the modern Information and Communication (ICT) Technology age, artificial intelligence should be used in all areas of libraries to facilitate effective and quicker library operation and service delivery.
- ii. All libraries are required to train and retrain all employees on using artificial intelligence in the library system.
- iii. Annual financial funding for training should be included in the tertiary institutions' budget so that workers in all other departments can receive training on how to apply

artificial intelligence in their departments. This would promote rapid service delivery.

- iv. Artificial intelligence has to be included at all levels of the national education curricula so that graduates from these institutions may work in every industry and use their knowledge of AI to advance the country.

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